

USE OF MODERN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE SYSTEM OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORT

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Abstract. *The state considers innovative educational technologies that contribute to the organization and formation of information competence of future specialists in physical culture and sports.. The main tasks of the development of the system of the educational process as one of the characteristics of quality education are considered. The main need to consider the readiness of teachers to implement the intellectual, professional and physical development of the individual and the use of modern information technologies in the system of training the professional activities of specialists.*

Keywords: *information competence, information technologies of education, strategies for using information technologies, quality of education.*

At present, the progress of the advanced countries of the world is based on the concept of cultural, intellectual, professional and physical development of the potential of the individual. The main place in solving development problems is given to the education system, one of the main tools of which are modern information technologies. Therefore, the informatization of education is of great importance. A specialist of any profile, including a specialist in the field of physical culture and sports, for free orientation in information flows must be able to receive, process and use information using computers, telecommunications and other information technology tools. This is impossible without the inclusion of an information component in the system of training and retraining of a modern specialist. The problem of training specialists in the field of physical culture and sports acquires a number of new aspects firstly in connection with the transition of the domestic education system to a model of multi-level training, and secondly, in connection with the need to implement the conceptual provisions of the state educational standard of higher professional education.

There are certain difficulties associated with the organizational, logistical, scientific and methodological aspects of the development and implementation of modern information technologies. In the field of physical culture and sports, there is a need, along with traditional means, to use modern information technologies that allow more efficient collection and processing of information transfers. Conduct independent work and self-education qualitatively change the content, methods and organizational forms of education, training of highly qualified athletes and judges, in conducting physical culture and health work with the population.

In this regard, the scientific search for the creation and use of modern information technologies in the educational and training process is of particular relevance. An important role in these transformations is played by the rapid development of scientific and technological progress, global technologization and informatization of the advanced countries of the world community. The processes taking place in connection with the informatization of society contribute to the intellectualization of various types of activities, which makes it possible to create a qualitatively new information environment that ensures the development of the individual's creative potential. Depending on the field of human activity, the specific professional

tasks he solves, the use of information technology has its own features and directions. At present, the progress of the advanced countries of the world is based on the concept of cultural, intellectual, professional and physical development of the individual.

The purpose of using modern information technologies is to create a new information and educational space for mastering physical culture specialists. The unified information space affected the entire learning process. The exchange of information resources has become a reality of the integration of the education system in modern conditions. The use of information technology in the teaching of higher educational institutions has not left aside physical culture. Modernization of pedagogical activity has become one of the steps to improve the process of physical education at all levels of education.

The use of modern information technologies in the field of physical culture is primarily aimed at increasing efficiency along with traditional means, ensuring the educational process and further practical activities of specialists. The main place in solving development problems is given to the education system, one of the main tools of which are modern information technologies. They allow you to change the system properties of the most important components of our existence, the development of strategies and the use of information technologies in the field of education, physical culture. Despite the difficulties associated with the organizational scientific and methodological aspects of the development and implementation of modern information technologies.

In the field of physical education, they are of particular interest to a number of specialists in the field of physical education and sports. Since there is a need to move from traditional forms of training aimed primarily at the accumulation of certain knowledge and skills.

The use of modern information technologies makes it possible to carry out the collection, processing and transmission of information much more effectively, to conduct independent work and self-education, to qualitatively change the content, methods and organizational forms of education.

Computer technologies as a part of information technologies form a fundamentally different style of learning activity, which turns out to be more comfortable, mobilizing creative possibilities and intellectual potential of students. After all, the activity of people increasingly depends on their awareness, the ability to effectively use information. For free orientation in information flows, a modern specialist of any profile must be able to receive, process and use information using computers, telecommunications and other information technology tools. The society's need for qualified specialists who own an arsenal of means and methods of informatics is turning into a leading factor in educational policy. A holistic implementation of this need is impossible without the inclusion of an information component in the training system of a future specialist. The main idea of using modern information technologies in the system of training and professional activities of specialists in physical culture. It consists in qualitatively transforming their educational and practical activities in the modern information world community.

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